

Deliverable 6.1 – WP6

Data Management Plan

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Prepared	Fabiana Arduini (UNITOV)	26.07.2024
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Acronyms and Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifiers
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
OoC	Organ-on-Chip
WPs	Work Packages

1. INTRODUCTION

This document provides the data management plan (DMP) for the PHOENIX-OoC project including detailed descriptions of data for each WP, outlining the specific tasks and responsibilities assigned to each partner for delivering an effective plan. The document explains the data repository and management, defining a secure store with two-factor authentication to protect sensitive information. The open access repository for information to be shared is selected, aligning with the EC Open Science policies. The FAIR Data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) will be respected, ensuring the high quality and utility of the data produced for an effective sharing and re-use of data between the scientific community and other stakeholders. Additionally, the risk management strategies are reported, identifying potential risks and proposing mitigation measures to adopt for helping in managing risks that could impact the project. Within the DMP, the coordinator formulated and distributed a questionnaire to each WP Leader to receive information regarding data management, such as the re-use and generation of the expected data in terms of origin, type, size, and format of the data.

2. WPs DATA DESCRIPTION

Each WP defines specific tasks to carry out within the WP. The WP leader is responsible for coordinating and monitoring all tasks and activities related to their WP. The WP leader ensures the work progresses according to plan, addressing any issues that arise and making necessary adjustments to keep the project on track. It is crucial that the WP leader gives information regarding data re-use and production. WP leaders are also responsible for the risk management process associated with their WP. The WP leaders are reported in Table 1, while Table 2 reports the list of contacts for each partner. Each institution leader will update the coordinator for any change regarding the contacts.

Table 1. List of WP leaders

WP	WP leader	Institution	e-mail
1	Javier Ramón Azcón	IBEC-CERCA	jramon@ibecbarcelona.eu
2	Arduini Fabiana	UNITOV	fabiana.arduini@uniroma2.it
3	Kersti Hermansson	UU	kersti@kemi.uu.se

4	Valentina Basoli	UNIBAS	valentina.basoli@unibas.ch
5	Goran Stojanović	FTN	sgoran@uns.ac.rs
6	Arduini Fabiana	UNITOV	fabiana.arduini@uniroma2.it
7	Arduini Fabiana	UNITOV	fabiana.arduini@uniroma2.it

Table 2. List of contacts for each partner

Name	Company	e-mail
Arduini Fabiana	UNITOV	fabiana.arduini@uniroma2.it
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Kersti Hermansson	UU	kersti@kemi.uu.se
Valentina Basoli	UNIBAS	valentina.basoli@unibas.ch
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Mònica Cunill Abancó	IBEC-CERCA	mcunill@ibecbarcelona.eu
Luca Fiore	SENSE	luca.fiore@sense4med.com

2.1 WP1

WP1 focuses on isolating cells from human joint tissue biopsies to perform the phenotypic characterization of these cells (UNIBAS). Additionally, this WP involves the fabrication of a paper-based pad to create ready-to-use cellular pads. For the PAD configuration, the necessary shape is selected by IBEC-CERCA in collaboration with UNITOV and SENSE, having experience in paper-based devices. To fabricate a paper-based pad, cryogelation technique will be used to achieve a three-dimensional porous structure characterized by high water content, microporous structure, and tunable pore sizes. Other tasks involve the optimization of cell seeding and thawing/freezing of cell culture. The mechanical properties of the paper pad seeded with cells will be assessed through IT-AFM. In this WP previous experimental data are re-used and new data such as text, image, measurement data, movie, presentations, articles, posters, and prototypes are expected.

2.2 WP2

WP2 is dedicated to developing paper-based microfluidics and paper-based array sensors (Lead: UNITOV, Participants: FTN, SENSE). The activity involves the delivery of:

- i) Paper-based microfluidic patterns to manage the fluids in a controlled way in the absence of an external pump and to avoid the bubble issue;
- ii) New configuration based on an electrochemical cell constituted of a printed reference electrode surrounded by seven working electrodes properly functionalized with sensitive nanomaterials/biocomponents to detect oxygen, glucose, lactate, lactate dehydrogenase, nitric oxide, nitrate, and pH for the measurement of inflammatory variation close the cells.

In WP2, existing data found in literature or originating from past projects of partners are re-used as a starting point. In this WP, new data such as text, images, measurement data, movies, presentations, articles, posters, and prototypes are expected.

2.3 WP3

WP3 involves molecular dynamics simulations to evaluate the type of cellulose to avoid the adsorption of drugs on paper layers. Additionally, this WP includes examining the behavior of oxygen within the PHOENIX-OoC device to better understand its impact on the experimental outcomes (Lead: UU, Participants: FTN, UNIBAS, UNITOV). Both standard molecular dynamics simulations and so-called metadynamics simulations of the cellulose-molecule and cellulose-solution interfaces will be performed. The oxygen reactivity at the surface will be explored through tight-binding DFT techniques. For this WP, the reuse of literature data is fundamental. Furthermore, the production of new data, including text, images, measurement data, presentations, articles, and posters coming from modeling studies, is expected.

2.4 WP4

WP4 is focused on the development of the PHOENIX-OoC device combining a paper-based cell pad, origami configuration, microfluidics, and a paper-based (bio)sensor array (Lead: UNIBAS, Participant: UNITOV, SENSE, IBEC-CERCA, FTN). WP4 includes testing the response of the different tissues to anti-inflammatory drugs. All assessments will be performed considering both homogeneous tissues (i.e. only cartilage pads and only bone pads) and joint-on-chip co-cultures.

Results will be compared to analogous studies made in the mechanical OA cartilage-on-chip model, using a PDMS-based device previously published by UNIBAS.

In this WP, new data such as text, images, measurement data, movies, presentations, articles, posters, and prototypes are expected.

2.5 WP5

WP5 aims to define and implement a comprehensive communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy for the PHOENIX-OoC project. The activity within WP5 will ensure that the project findings and innovations are effectively shared with the broader scientific community and other relevant stakeholders. Dissemination and Communication activities (Lead: FTN, Participants: UNITOV, IBEC-CERCA, UU, UNIBAS, SENSE) include i) publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals in open access, ii) presentation of the project results at national/international scientific meetings, conferences, and workshops, iii) organization of public meetings, cultural events, discussion groups within communities, and iv) organization of 2 workshops. A final plan for using and disseminating the knowledge acquired within PHOENIX-OoC will be provided at the end of the project. This WP also deals with the exploitation plan and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection strategies (Lead: SENSE, Participant: UNIBAS). The exploitation of results is considered at different levels of the project to ensure the appropriate implementation of IPR strategy and its revision during the whole course of the project. The scientific outcomes will be disseminated in conferences as presentations or posters, images or text files and will appear in international refereed scientific journals prepared as text document files. In addition, image files, newspaper articles or videos will be published on the website <https://www.phoenixooc.com>.

2.6 WP6

WP6 ensures efficient administration of the project in accordance with European Commission guidelines and requirements.¹ This WP facilitates communication among the Consortium members to ensure smooth collaboration and project progress (Lead: UNITOV, Participants: FTN, IBEC-CERCA, UU, UNIBAS, SENSE). The outputs of WP6 include economic data, personal data, deliverables related to the DMP, risk management documents, quality monitoring, and other legal documents. For example, for the monitoring of financial management, a file detailing the incurred costs has been made and shared in PHOENIX-OoC consortium. These documents are gathered

throughout the entire duration of PHOENIX-OoC, with contributions from the entire Consortium for coordination and reporting purposes. The quality of deliverables and milestones will be assessed by adding the internal quality control carried out by the partner(s) selected by the coordinator for each deliverable and milestone, as reported in Table 3. This WP also focuses on risk management which includes identifying, quantifying, responding, controlling and reporting risk by creating contingency/mitigation plans.

Table 3. List of deliverables and milestones with quality control

Deliverable/ Milestones	Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date (month)	Quality Control
D1.1	Cell-culture interim results	WP1	6 – UNIBAS	12	IBEC-CERCA
D1.2	Cell-pad configuration interim results	WP1	5 – SENSE	6	UNITOV
D1.3	Cell culture	WP1	6 – UNIBAS	28	IBEC-CERCA
D1.4	Cell-pad configuration	WP1	5 – SENSE	28	UNITOV
D1.5	Cell-pad	WP1	2 – IBEC-CERCA	28	UNIBAS
D1.6	Paper-tissue	WP1	6 – UNIBAS	28	IBEC-CERCA
D2.1	Microfluidics	WP2	4 – FTN	28	UNITOV
D2.2	Sensor test	WP2	1 – UNITOV	28	SENSE
D3.1	Modelling for oxygen interim results	WP3	3 – UU	12	FTN
D3.2	Modelling for drugs	WP3	3 – UU	34	UNIBAS
D3.3	Modelling for oxygen	WP3	3 – UU	34	UNITOV
D3.4	Modelling reactivity	WP3	3 – UU	34	SENSE
D4.1	OoC integration	WP4	5 – SENSE	30	UNITOV
D4.2	Validation of OA joint-on-chip model	WP4	6 – UNIBAS	32	SENSE
D4.3	Drug testing	WP4	6 – UNIBAS	35	UNITOV
D4.4	Impact	WP4	1 – UNITOV	35	FTN

D5.1	Website and Project logo	WP5	4 – FTN	2	UNITOV
D5.2	Plan for Dissemination and Communications Activities	WP5	4 – FTN	6	SENSE
D5.3	Plan for Exploitation Activities	WP5	5 – SENSE	6	FTN
D5.4	Final version of Plan for Dissemination and Communication Activities	WP5	4 – FTN	36	UNITOV
D5.5	Final Version of Plan for Exploitation Activities	WP5	5 – SENSE	36	UNIBAS
D6.1	Data Management Plan	WP6	1 – UNITOV	6	FTN
D6.2	RP1 Technical/scientific review meeting documents	WP6	1 – UNITOV	13	FTN
D6.3	RP2 Technical/Scientific review meeting documents	WP6	1 – UNITOV	36	FTN
D6.4	RP2 updated of the Data Management Plan	WP6	1 – UNITOV	36	FTN
D7.1	OEI – Requirement No. 1	WP7	1 – UNITOV	1	FTN
D7.2	OEI – Requirement No. 2	WP7	1 – UNITOV	12	UNIBAS
D7.3	OEI – Requirement No. 3	WP7	1 – UNITOV	24	UNIBAS
D7.4	OEI – Requirement No. 4	WP7	1 – UNITOV	36	UNIBAS
M.1	Paper-based tissue ready	WP1	2-IBEC-CERCA	28	UNIBAS
M.2	Paper-based components ready	WP2	1-UNITOV	28	FTN
M.3	Free-energy modelling achieved	WP3	3-UU	34	SENSE
M.4	OoC tested with drugs	WP4	6-UNIBAS	35	IBEC-CERCA

2.7 WP7

WP7 aims to guarantee that all activities observe the ethical requirements plan for the project (Lead: UNITOV). This involves providing guidelines to ensure adherence to ethical standards, as a comprehensive documentation about the ethical considerations surrounding using waste material from human sources within the PHOENIX-OoC project. Furthermore, within the ethics documents, we include the protocols and procedures for obtaining informed consent, protecting privacy rights, and ensuring the dignity and respect of individuals involved in procuring and using human waste material.

3. DATA SUMMARY

Research Data Management is a critical point to guarantee the integrity, reproducibility, security, and accessibility of the research data generated within this project, so it is necessary to list the practices to manage research data.

For adequate data management, information was collected from all partners (via a questionnaire of sorts) regarding details about their data types and storage spaces needed in relation to the PHOENIX-OoC project. The information collected was used to create a useful data space for our project.

Questions addressed to partners are listed below:

 Questionnaire

Dear PHOENIX-OoC partner,

This questionnaire invites you to share details about the data storage spaces you need related to the PHOENIX-OoC project. The information collected will be used to create a useful space for our project data.

Thank you for your time and helping us get the information we need for PHOENIX-OoC data management.

- Will you use any pre-existing data, and for what purpose?
- What kinds and formats of data do you plan to produce?
- How much data (and of what size) do you plan to produce?
- What is the provenance of the generated or re-used data (literature, manufactory, experiments...)?
- Are there any legitimate reasons that might limit open access to the data generated by PHOENIX-OoC, as outlined in the Grant Agreement?
- Who outside your project might find your data useful?

In response to this questionnaire, it is highlighted that a part of project work consists in re-use of existing data (literature and previous experiment data) where relevant, primarily for comparative analysis and to build upon previous research. The project will generate unique scientific and technological data (including experimental results, literature data, and manufacturing data), which we expect will attract interest from many laboratories. The questionnaire showed that there will be approximately 1 TB of data, and the formats include:

- stl format for design for 3D printing process;
- cvs format for instruments for electrical characterization;
- mov format of movies for recording;
- jpg/tiff format of photos;
- xlsx format of measurements data;
- mp4 experimental set-up recordings;
- docx format of experimental description and initial versions of official documents;
- pptx experiment presentations and images;

- ptx GraphPad Prizm software data format for experimental data processing;
- pdf format for final versions of official documents.

The data generated in the PHOENIX-OoC project will be useful not only to project partners, but also to other researchers and stakeholders who can benefit from project results and methodologies. Therefore, after the evaluation of patentability, some project data will be Open Access in line with the project policies; indeed, any legitimate interests or constraints, such as IPR or confidentiality agreements, which may limit this Open Access policy are also considered. In this context, it is important to emphasize that raw data, without needing IPR or scientific relevance, are private data. Thus, the owner of these data is responsible for their security and storage in local archives, which will not be shared.

The sensitive data such as logos, document templates, legal documents, deliverables, milestones, various report versions, meeting agendas, meeting minutes, and shared meeting data will be classified as internal data within the Consortium. For this type of data, SharePoint of Microsoft Office 365 has been chosen as the cloud storage being widely used and specifically designed for secure, real-time file/data storage, sharing, and collaboration. SharePoint is a multi-tenant hyperscale cloud platform providing combined services. Moreover, Office 365 allows customers to choose the region for their data storage, ensuring that Microsoft only replicates data within the chosen geographic area for resiliency and not beyond it. The initial cloud capacity (storage space purchased by SENSE: 1TB, as requested by the questionnaire) will be expanded as needed, based on the data produced, which may deviate from what was anticipated in the questionnaire response. The service is administered by SENSE, but all project partners have access and editing rights to the files stored in SharePoint.

The SharePoint site for the PHOENIX-OoC project is organized into eleven subfolders (Figure 1), where each partner can easily access the documents and images they need. The folders contain:

- i) A space for proposal for brief interviews with experts as decided in the kick-off meeting;
- ii) The data relating to the Consortium;
- iii) The data partners with their contacts;
- iv) The final deliverables;
- v) The logo, the material for the dissemination and communication activities, and a template for the reporting dissemination event;

- vi) The ethics advisor;
- vii) A file for the management and monitoring of financial resources;
- viii) The Grant Agreement;
- ix) All the documents relating to the meetings (Figure 2);
- x) The final reporting periods
- xi) The documents related to the WPs.

Access to SharePoint is through the URL: <https://sense4med.sharepoint.com/sites/Arduini>, using a web browser. To grant access to project participants, the system administrator sends invitations to their e-mails. Access is granted when participants visit the site for the first time. Permissions within the intranet sections are finely defined, ensuring each participant has appropriate access levels to lists, document libraries, folders, or documents.

Figure 1. Organizing data in SharePoint

Figure 2. Meetings documents

Finally, in accordance with the Open Access policy of the European Community, the partners are invited to share their data in green and gold open access. Although gold open access mode is preferred, the project holds both models to facilitate the dissemination activity.

For all data intended to be Open Access, such as those relating to the project communication and dissemination activities, scientific articles, conference presentations, posters, and open-source documentation, it is possible to use the storage space specially designed for the publication of Open Access data in accordance with EU guidelines: Zenodo. In Zenodo platform, we have our community, called Phoenix-OoC project (Figure 3), and each uploaded dataset/record cannot exceed 50GBs in size, but the platform provides free unlimited data space for its users. In addition to Zenodo, public products and communication materials, including images, videos, links to scientific articles and more, can be uploaded to the project website, making them accessible to the public for the duration of PHOENIX-OoC and four years-beyond.

Figure 3. PHOENIX-OoC project community in Zenodo

4. DATA SECURITY

The activities made under the Horizon Europe Programme must fulfil the applicable security rules within Commission Decision (EU, Euratom) 2015/444, and its implementing rules.

SharePoint of Microsoft 365 is a cloud storage solution designer for secure and efficient file/data storage, sharing, and real-time collaboration. It is widely utilized in EU projects, making it the ideal choice for this data layer, following the Regulation (EU) 2016/679.²

It is possible to restrict access to SharePoint sites and content to users in a specific group by using site access restriction policies. Users who are not part of the specified group cannot access the site or its content, even if they previously had permissions or a shared link. Microsoft technicians administer SharePoint and OneDrive through a PowerShell console that requires two-factor authentication.³

Data security for EU projects using Microsoft 365 SharePoint involves several key measures to guarantee the security of sensitive data. These measures include:

- Planned Access and Permission, assign permissions based on user roles;
- Data Encryption using advanced encryption standards with BitLocker;
- Compliance with EU Regulations (GDPR);³
- Multi-Factor Authentication;
- Audit Logs and Monitoring, including access and modifications to data;
- Data Backup and Recovery.⁴

By implementing these measures, SENSE and other project partners can ensure that data stored and shared via Microsoft SharePoint remains secure and compliant with EU regulations, ensuring its availability for at least four years beyond the end of PHOENIX-OoC project.

5. OPEN-DATA REPOSITORY

In accordance with the Open Access policy of the European Community, the partners are invited to share their data in Green and Gold Open Access models.

- Gold Open Access is related to publication in open access journals for having article immediately available to the public.
- Green Open Access involves self-archiving research outputs in an institutional or subject repository.

For the PHOENIX-OoC EU project, this means that all partners are encouraged to deposit a version of their peer-reviewed articles, conference papers, and other scholarly outputs in an accessible repository. For this purpose, Zenodo was identified as a repository meeting the needs of the project (Figure 4).

Zenodo is an Open Access repository developed by CERN under the OpenAIRE project to support the long-tail of research results in various disciplines and providing a platform for researchers to upload, share, and preserve publications, datasets, software, and other research materials.⁵

Figure 4. Zenodo repository

Access to Zenodo is through the URL: <https://zenodo.org>, using a web browser. It is possible to search for our community among all simply by searching for *Phoenix-OoC project* and our logo is easily recognizable in the interface (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Our community in Zenodo

The site allows visitors to search, preview, and download Open Access items without logging in. To upload and publish content or use advanced services, users must register for free. Users can log in directly with their ORCID or GitHub accounts or sign up using a valid email address (Figure 6). One of the standout features of Zenodo is the assignment of Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) to each uploaded item. These persistent identifiers make research outputs citable and easily discoverable, enhancing their visibility and academic impact. Once the community is found, and after registering and logging in, it is possible to upload material, which will then be visible to the rest of the community members upon approval by the community manager. In our case, the *Phoenix-OoC project* community is administered by the coordinator: UNITOV. During the data deposition procedure, the uploaded item can be linked to PHOENIX-OoC project, and the administrator is notified to accept or reject the inclusion of the record into the community.

Figure 6. Zenodo log-in interface

6. FAIR DATA

FAIR data are data which meet principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.⁶ PHOENIX-OoC provides experimental research data following FAIR principles.

6.1 Making data findable

The cured data produced in the project related to research results will be shared on Zenodo to make the research results easily findable, improving their visibility and academic impact. Metadata are provided with relevant keywords to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential

re-use, they include descriptive metadata (e.g. title, authors, abstract, keywords, publication date), administrative metadata, and technical metadata (as information on data ownership, rights management, licensing, and access restrictions).

6.2 Making data accessible

The project partners guarantee the data accessibility, after considering IPR, by publishing it in Gold Open Access or Green Open Access. For better sharing, the cured datasets and research results are deposited in the ZENODO open data repository (see section 5) for the entire duration of the project and at least four years after PHOENIX-OoC end. The data are stored in open file formats and clear instructions are provided on how to access and manage these datasets. The metadata is also openly available and licensed in the public domain and remains available for at least four years after project closure on the project website (<https://www.phoenixooc.com>) and Zenodo repository.

6.3 Making data interoperable

Data are stored in open file formats, and clear instructions on how to access and manage these datasets are provided. Moreover, data include references to other data such as datasets from previous research activities.

6.4 Increase data re-use

Documentation, including a readme file, is provided to prevent misuse or misinterpretation and to maintain data integrity. A data license is mandatory and DATPROF used for data generation and validation. Part of the data produced in PHOENIX-OoC are utilizable by third parties, and part of the data will be under patent.

Principles

Best Effort Principles

Zenodo does not sign SLAs (service-level agreements). This is not a weakness, it is by design and marks a philosophy that we believe is most appropriate for Science. Instead, Zenodo is run by leading practitioners according to best practices.

What Science needs is inherent reliability, or more accurately demonstrated reliability based on open best practices. Furthermore the users should be able to influence these best practices. In the long-term, a service which is trusted is much more valuable than one for which assurances must be bought.

Service failure can never be undone. Enforcing an SLA means being prepared to litigate against the contract, which means compensation, frequently assessed on the basis of loss of revenue... but none of these concepts have any place or relevance in the free exchange of research results!

Living by these principles, Zenodo strives to make available architecture, implementation, practices and statistics. Please see for example the infrastructure page. We are also aiming to have these certified.

FAIR Principles

FAIR Principles definition as referenced from: *Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci. Data 3:160018 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18 (2016).*

To be Findable:

- **F1:** (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
 - A DOI is issued to every published record on Zenodo.
- **F2:** data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
 - Zenodo's metadata is compliant with [DataCite's Metadata Schema](#) minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments.
- **F3:** metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
 - The DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record.
- **F4:** (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
 - Metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing.
 - Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

To be Accessible:

- **A1:** (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the [OAI-PMH](#) protocol by the record identifier and the collection name.
 - Metadata is also retrievable through the public [REST API](#).
- **A1.1:** the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - See point A1. OAI-PMH and REST are open, free and universal protocols for information retrieval on the web.
- **A1.2:** the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
 - Metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it.
- **A2:** metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
 - Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.
 - Metadata are stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which are separate to the data itself.

To be Interoperable:

- **I1:** (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
 - Zenodo uses [JSON Schema](#) as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as [Dublin Core](#) or [MARCXML](#).
- **I2:** (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
 - For certain terms we refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license ([Open Definition](#)), funders ([FundRef](#)) and grants ([OpenAIRE](#)).
- **I3:** (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
 - Each referenced external piece of metadata is qualified by a resolvable URL.

To be Reusable:

- **R1:** (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - Each record contains a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite recommended terms and Zenodo's enrichments.
- **R1.1:** (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata, and is referring to an [Open Definition](#) license.
 - Data downloaded by the users is subject to the license specified in the metadata by the uploader.
- **R1.2:** (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - All data and metadata uploaded is traceable to a registered Zenodo user.
 - Metadata can optionally describe the original authors of the published work.
- **R1.3:** (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards
 - Zenodo is not a domain-specific repository, yet through compliance with DataCite's Metadata Schema, metadata meets one of the broadest cross-domain standards available.

Figure 7. FAIR Principles reported in Zenodo website ⁶

7. RISK MANAGEMENT

The risk management is crucial to the development of the project, particularly in innovative fields of the OoC. Innovation is always associated with risk in fact, in the literature, there are many models for risk management.⁸ Therefore, the complexity and novelty of the PHOENIX-OoC project require a robust risk management strategy to identify, evaluate, and mitigate potential risks that may occur. This section outlines the risk management strategy adopted by the PHOENIX-OoC Consortium: UNITOV, together with partners, has established a risk methodology that includes risk identification, quantification, response, control, and reporting. The primary goal is to abide by the project's objectives, timelines, and deliverables, while maximizing the potential for innovation and scientific advancement.

Table 5 provides a list of the critical risks associated with the PHOENIX-OoC project (as listed in the Grant Agreement) and the proposed mitigation measures for each risk. These risks span various WPs and highlight potential challenges in extending cellular life span, controlling flow rates, ensuring cell adhesion and survival, maintaining sensor performance, simulation efficiency, accuracy of drug testing, and stakeholder involvement. It is essential to highlight that the risk management is a continuous process throughout the life of the project. Risk management is the responsibility of all Consortium partners, each WP leader has the responsibility to inform the project coordinator of any new risk identified. Any changes to the results schedule or the assigned budget must be conveyed to the WP leader, who will submit a modification request to the coordinator. If deemed necessary, the coordinator will inform the Project Officer.

Table 4. Critical risks & risk management strategy

Critical risks & risk management strategy			
Risk number	Description	Work Package No(s)	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1	Failure in extending the cellular life span of human articular joint cells; Likelihood: Medium; Severity: Medium.	WP1	Inclusion of various donors and isolation of cells from different tissues (healthy as well as OA patients with varying numbers of population doublings that can be reached) to increase the possibility of isolating enough cells.

2	Uncontrolled flow rate; Likelihood: Medium; Severity: Medium.	WP2	The flow rate is affected by the presence of novel cell-paper pad. The use of origami devices will control the flow rate by inserting different layers with different configurations.
3	Low adhesion of cells and high mortality in the internal layers; Likelihood: Medium; Severity: Medium.	WP2	Limited adhesion could be due to the limited amount of compound that binds the cellulose paper. Increasing the quantity of recombinant protein or using commercial fibronectin, collagen can improve cell adhesion.
4	High mortality during freezing and thawing; Likelihood: Medium; Severity: High.	WP2	Cells in adhesion on the pad could risk detaching during freezing process. We will add conventional method with DMSO (gold standard) to avoid crystal formation. Mortality will be evaluated by cell titer blue, live and dead assay.
5	Low analytical performances of the sensor array in terms of robustness (i.e. working stability), sensitivity (i.e. high detection limit); Likelihood: Medium; Severity: Medium.	WP2	The working stability will be improved by selecting the proper enzyme immobilization of the enzymes, selecting the chemical immobilization instead of physical adsorption. The sensitivity will be enough using the nanomaterials such as carbon black, in the case increased sensitivity is required, other nanomaterials will be used such as graphene/MXene.
6	Some simulations might become very time-consuming to converge. Likelihood: Medium; Severity: Medium	WP3	We will replace the DFT calculations with the faster and more approximate tight-binding DFT calculations, at least at a first stage. We have previously used this method with good outcomes results when correctly parametrized.
7	Uncorrected drug testing with paper-based PHOENIX OoC. Likelihood: Medium; Severity: Medium.	WP4	UNIBAS has wide expertise in drug screening, internal control on cells seed on conventional 2D plates and OoC Gold standard will be used for identifying uncorrected drug administration during PHOENIX-OoC development.
8	Unable to involve stakeholders to participate in the project dissemination and exploitation; Likelihood: M; Severity: M.	WP5	Stakeholders will be frequently engaged through D&C activities, in view of promoting project results and its benefits in different sectors.

The purpose of this table is to predict risks, so by addressing these risks with detailed mitigation strategies, the project aims to ensure successful progress. Each mitigation measure is designed to prevent the occurrence of the risk or minimize its impact, improving the robustness and resistance

of the project. As the project evolves, continuous monitoring and adaptive risk management will be key to addressing the challenges inherent in this innovative research.

8. CONCLUSION

The questionnaire submitted to the partners and the European Guidelines allowed us to provide information on the fundamental elements of data management to build the PHOENIX-OoC DMP. The aim is to provide i) an overview of the generation and reuse of the data that the PHOENIX-OoC project will produce and will be reused; ii) the reasons for processing and analyzing the data within PHOENIX-OoC project's objectives (so how the data supports the project objectives, the expected results from the data processing and how these results align with the project mission); iii) the identification of the potential audience that will benefit from the project results, including researchers, industry professionals, politicians, companies, and the scientific community in general. Understanding the target audience helps adapt the data management and dissemination strategies to meet their needs effectively. Furthermore, a description of the technologies and tools used to ensure the safe deposition, sharing, and maintenance of data during and after the duration of PHOENIX-OoC project has been included. This covers data storage solutions, sharing platforms and security actions to defend the integrity and confidentiality of the PHOENIX-OoC data produced, which adhere to the FAIR principles.

Additionally, the table of critical risks and risk management strategy serves as a reference for the Consortium partners during the execution of the project. The critical risks will be updated in D6.2 RP1 Technical/Scientific review meeting (month 13) for the first update. As the PHOENIX-OoC project evolves and matures, this data management plan will be finalized in D6.4 (month 36).

9. REFERENCES

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10. ANNEX 1

PARTNER: IBEC-CERCA

Questionnaire

Dear PHOENIX-OoC partner,

This questionnaire invites you to share details about the data storage spaces you need related to the PHOENIX-OoC project. The information collected will be used to create a useful space for our project data.

Thank you for your time and helping us get the information we need for PHOENIX-OoC data management.

 Will you use any pre-existing data, and for what purpose?

The initial parameters for fabricating the scaffolds are to establish a starting point for producing the scaffolds in the optimal condition for cell culturing.

 What kinds and formats of data do you plan to produce?

Numerical data and images

 How much data (and of what size) do you plan to produce?

- Designing requirements of the scaffold and their platform to fabricate it < 10 GB
- Validation of the scaffolds using SEM, rheometry and imaging < 10 GB
- Data on the cell cultivation inside the scaffold < 50 GB

 What is the provenance of the generated or re-used data (literature, manufactory, experiments...)?

Both, literature and manufactory experiments

 Are there any legitimate reasons that might limit open access to the data generated by PHOENIX-OoC, as outlined in the Grant Agreement?

To include the data in a patent

 Who outside your project might find your data useful?

The expected data generated in this project's framework is scientific and technological. Given the absence of equivalent technologies, we expect this technique to attract the interest of several laboratories. Thus, we expect to establish new collaborations and consider proof-of-concept strategies to transfer this technology to the market. As such, we expect our findings to have a far-reaching impact on basic research and appeal to engineers and biologists alike.

PARTNER: FTN

Questionnaire

Dear PHOENIX-OoC partner,

This questionnaire invites you to share details about the data storage spaces you need related to the PHOENIX-OoC project. The information collected will be used to create a useful space for our project data.

Thank you for your time and helping us get the information we need for PHOENIX-OoC data management.

 Will you use any pre-existing data, and for what purpose?

Yes. Data of parameters for machine calibrations that we already have in the lab from previous research work.

 What kinds and formats of data do you plan to produce?

stl format for design of microfluidics chips which should be fabricated by 3D printing process

cvs format for instruments which we will use for electrical characterization

mov format of movies for recording the flow through our microfluidic chips

jpg format of photos of microfluidic chips fabricated

xlsx format of watability measurements data

avi format of watability measurements recordings, microfluidic experiments recordings

mp4 experimental set-up recordings

docx format of experimental description

pptx experiment presentations and colage images

ptfx GraphPad Prizm software data format for experimental data processing

 How much data (and of what size) do you plan to produce?

- Movies – up to 2 GB
- Experimental recordings and data - up to 1 TB

 What is the provenance of the generated or re-used data (literature, manufactory, experiments...)?

 The origin of our data will be from our fabrication data and experimental testing and characterization in our lab.

 Are there any legitimate reasons that might limit open access to the data generated by PHOENIX-OoC, as outlined in the Grant Agreement?

Only what we plan to patent.

 Who outside your project might find your data useful?

From publications, everyone, it will be in open repository.

PARTNER: UNIBAS

Questionnaire

Dear PHOENIX-OoC partner,

This questionnaire invites you to share details about the data storage spaces you need related to the PHOENIX-OoC project. The information collected will be used to create a useful space for our project data.

Thank you for your time and helping us get the information we need for PHOENIX-OoC data management.

 Will you use any pre-existing data, and for what purpose?

We are initially using protocols for isolating cells from bovine knee tissue, with the goal of ultimately working on human knee tissue. These protocols were previously used, but they are now being optimized for the purpose of the project.

 What kinds and formats of data do you plan to produce?

Numerical data based on Excel exported or .TXT and images as original file (depending the different instruments) or exported in .TIFF and .JPEG. In regard of image original files can be open always with free software Imagej/Fijii

 How much data (and of what size) do you plan to produce?

1. Picture for quality control using Confocal and SEM, Histological optical microscopy > 10 GB
2. qPCR analysis and ELISA biochemical analysis, Cell titer, < 10 GB
3. Data on the cell cultivation inside PHOENIX-OoC vs Gold Standard (Pictures, biochemical outcome) > 20 GB

 What is the provenance of the generated or re-used data (literature, manufactory, experiments...)?

Previous published data and new experiments according to the tasks and deliverables

 Are there any legitimate reasons that might limit open access to the data generated by PHOENIX-OoC, as outlined in the Grant Agreement?

To include the data in a patent

 Who outside your project might find your data useful?

The PHOENIX-OoC project has high translational potential at a commercial level. In fact, both technologically and biologically, it could have an excellent market, targeting laboratories conducting toxicological studies for both drugs and materials. In the long term, the vision supporting the PHOENIX-OoC prototype project is based

on the pump-free microfluidic system, which can be easily assembled in any laboratory that lacks advanced cell culture facilities and instrumentation for outcome analysis. Its strength lies in the possibility of self-assembling a tissue model by ordering pads with pre-incorporated cells, also enabling real-time monitoring of the toxicity of drugs or materials.

PARTNER: SENSE

Questionnaire

Dear PHOENIX-OoC partner,

This questionnaire invites you to share details about the data storage spaces you need related to the PHOENIX-OoC project. The information collected will be used to create a useful space for our project data.

Thank you for your time and helping us get the information we need for PHOENIX-OoC data management.

 Will you use any pre-existing data, and for what purpose?

Yes. We will utilize data from literature.

 What kinds and formats of data do you plan to produce?

pdf format for sensors device design

 How much data (and of what size) do you plan to produce?

Up to 100 Mb

 What is the provenance of the generated or re-used data (literature, manufactory, experiments...)?

The source of our data will be from existing literature.

 Are there any legitimate reasons that might limit open access to the data generated by PHOENIX-OoC, as outlined in the Grant Agreement?

Only the data we plan to patent.

 Who outside your project might find your data useful?

From publications, everyone, it will be in open repository.

PARTNER: UNITOV

Questionnaire

Dear PHOENIX-OoC partner,

This questionnaire invites you to share details about the data storage spaces you need related to the PHOENIX-OoC project. The information collected will be used to create a useful space for our project data.

Thank you for your time and helping us get the information we need for PHOENIX-OoC data management.

 Will you use any pre-existing data, and for what purpose?

Yes. We will utilize data obtained from our previous research work, as well as data gathered from relevant literature.

 What kinds and formats of data do you plan to produce?

Jpg/tiff format of photos and figures of paper-based sensor

xlsx format of measurements data

mp4 format for video

docx format of experimental description

pptx presentations for conference

pdf format for poster presentation and legal documents

 How much data (and of what size) do you plan to produce?

Up to 1 TB

 What is the provenance of the generated or re-used data (literature, manufactory, experiments...)?

The source of our data will be from our experiments conducted in the laboratory, as well as from existing literature.

 Are there any legitimate reasons that might limit open access to the data generated by PHOENIX-OoC, as outlined in the Grant Agreement?

Only the data we plan to patent.

 Who outside your project might find your data useful?

From publications, everyone, it will be in open repository.

PARTNER: UU

Questionnaire

Dear PHOENIX-OoC partner,

This questionnaire invites you to share details about the data storage spaces you need related to the PHOENIX-OoC project. The information collected will be used to create a useful space for our project data.

Thank you for your time and helping us get the information we need for PHOENIX-OoC data management.

Will you use any pre-existing data, and for what purpose?

We use experimental data of the atomic positions within cellulose systems (e.g. crystals) from the literature or from data-bases, when available and relevant. These are used as a starting configuration for calculations. In addition to structural data, existing force-field parameters from the literature will often be used in the setup of calculations. Another important category of pre-existing data are experimental results to be used for validation of our calculations. Such experimental data may originate from a range of experimental techniques such as diffraction and various spectroscopies, to name a few.

What kinds and formats of data do you plan to produce?

The data will be: selected numerical data (energies, structures, MD trajectories, etc), text and image data resulting from our calculations, mostly in the form of cured data. A range of formats will be used.

How much data (and of what size) do you plan to produce?

- Numerical data: e.g. trajectories of the order of Tbytes each
- Text and image data: < 10 GB
- structure and properties-databases < 5 GB

What is the provenance of the generated or re-used data (literature, manufactory, experiments...)?

Both experimental and computational results from the literature, and (primarily) in-group computational results from our team as well as experimental results from our PHOENIX-OoC colleagues.

 Are there any legitimate reasons that might limit open access to the data generated by PHOENIX-OoC, as outlined in the Grant Agreement?

The plan is to follow standard procedure in the scientific community and make results, models and selected cured data available.

 Who outside your project might find your data useful?

The data generated within this project will be both scientific and technical, providing both computational workflows and deeper insights into cellulose systems, cellulose-water interactions, and drug molecule interactions. The generated data will be valuable to a broad audience. More specifically,

- Cured reference data for repositories or interactive databases will be useful for the consortium and to a wider community.
- MD trajectories: Useful for the consortium and wider.
- Property and spectral predictions and assistance in the interpretation of experimental data. Useful for wide experimental communities
- Computational protocols, workflows and models. Useful for wide modelling communities.